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Abstract

This document summarises the publication of a technical service tool, to test and validate commercial cloud services for the benefit of scientific workloads in multiple domains developed by CERN under an AGPL license.

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Executive Summary

The objective of the test suite is to validate commercial cloud services for the benefit of scientific workloads in multiple domains. The development of the test suite originates from the HNSciCloud project, where automation was lacking as tests deployments were executed manually, in a scattered manner with no result tracking capabilities. The initial version of the test suite has been developed during the OCRE project, and successfully deployed in a number of cloud providers before the existence of the OCRE Framework.

Regarding the validation of cloud services under the OCRE Framework, access to the 27 cloud platforms present in OCRE will be necessary. To this end, CERN proposes to include an obligation to provide access to a billing account with a limited number of funds made available by the cloud vendors of the original 27 cloud platforms represented either directly or via resellers with contracts adjudicated through the OCRE Framework. This limited amount of funds will be used to validate cloud services in each of the platforms, to trial different configurations, billing controls, and to validate exit strategies.

The test suite developed by CERN under an AGPL license is expected to become part of best practice, and to be adopted for on-boarding commercial cloud services to research environments in the context of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

1 Introduction

CERN is coordinating and participating in a number of EC projects that involve the integration of research workloads with public cloud providers across Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) and Software as a Service (SaaS) stacks. To monitor the level of readiness of cloud providers against multidisciplinary scientific Research workloads, a technical benchmarking and validation process for commercial service providers has been created.

The methodology for this process leverages lessons learned from earlier projects such as HNSciCloud [1], it has been expanded in OCRE, and it is included in the general R&D validation framework in the ARCHIVER project [2]. Benchmark testing and validation range from IaaS cloud infrastructure (compute, storage, networking, and data ingests), and moves up in the cloud stack to SaaS. In OCRE, only IaaS is considered for validation since SaaS providers are not present in the OCRE Framework.

The test suite relies on open technologies. This aspect is considered a determining factor to stimulate the contribution of the research community. It relies on Terraform [3] and Ansible [4] for resource provisioning and configuration, and Docker [5] and Kubernetes [6] for the abstraction of deployments and orchestration.

The test validation suite is expected to be considered part of best practice and adopted for the onboarding of commercial cloud services for research environments in the context of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

The main purpose of the test validation suite is to test and validate commercial cloud services for the benefit of scientific workloads in multiple domains in an automated manner. The end user does not have to be proficient with cloud technologies to run the test suite.

The target audience of the test validation suite comprises all researchers, from individuals to members of medium to large organisations that perform research and would like to support their work with cloud services and capacity

This document is structured as follows:

- Section 2 describes the baseline from which the test suite was developed.
- Section 3 details the obtained validation test suite, its features, and capabilities.
- Section 4 sets out the test contribution process that test owners are required to follow.
- Section 5 provides an overview of events where the test suite has been presented.
- Section 6 details plans for future work.

- Section 7 offers conclusions and next steps.

2 Baseline

The test suite derives from the R&D activity that ten research performing organisations (CERN [7], EMBL-EBI [8], DESY [9], PIC [10], CNRS [11], STFC [12], ESRF [13], SURFsara [14], INFN [15] and KIT [16]) performed during the HNSciCloud project with European cloud providers. As part of the lessons learned of the project, a gap was identified in having a structured framework to run research workload validation, as part of a repeatable and tracked process. For example, provider A can have excellent results in running a 3DGAN Machine Learning simulation because they offer specialised infrastructure such as TensorFlow Processing Units (TPUs) [17] or Graphcore Intelligent Processing Units (IPUs) [18] but provider B lacks all these. The differences in the benchmarking results need to be systematically tracked, and the tool needs to have a degree of automation to be able to iterate deployments rapidly.

The following aspects were identified as part of the lessons learned of HNSciCloud regarding the conception of a testing validation tool:

- Automation

Lack of automation of the testing and validation process makes it very difficult to prepare tests and respective testbeds. A lot of effort has to be made to provision infrastructure, configure it, and run the test. It is also virtually impossible to reproduce and repeat runs as the full steps would have to be repeated several times, which is not sustainable. Therefore, automation is a key aspect to address.

- Abstraction

In relation to the previous point, in HNSciCloud it was not possible to bundle tests (i.e. containerise them). The testing process consisted of basic scripts written in several different languages. As a result, the deployment of these tests required heavy configuration of the hosts before these were able to host a test run, as there was no abstraction layer.

- Support for heterogeneous approaches

Research organisations carrying out tests and related service validation tasks often follow different approaches and/or methodologies. A certain degree of freedom is relevant and useful, however, if no balance is considered ensuring a common base methodology and a common approach, this can lead to fragmentation and be less effective considering the number of research teams normally involved in these activities.

- Centralised results repository

During the HNSciCloud testing activities, the obtained results were scattered across different supports and collected in a basic spreadsheet. A central repository for results in a format that would support a lightweight data-interchange format, both easy for humans to read and write, and for machines to parse and generate, is deemed necessary.

3 Test Suite Framework

This section details the obtained validation test suite, its features, and capabilities.

3.1 Developments in the Context of OCRE

This section provides a high-level overview of the main features of the tool. The full list of features the tool offers can be checked using the detailed documentation online [\[19\]](#).

3.1.1 Automation

An end-to-end automated deployment process has been developed. This is a core aspect of the validation tool. To run a test script on a cloud provider's IaaS platform, a user has to:

1. Provision infrastructure.
2. Configure the infrastructure.
3. Run a test.
4. Collect results.
5. Remove and clean up the created IaaS stack.

The developed validation automates these steps by using open technologies:

1. Provision infrastructure - done by Terraform, with predefined scripts written on its Hashicorp Configuration Language (HCL).
2. Configure the infrastructure - done by Ansible, with playbooks.
3. Run a test - done with Docker containers, orchestrated by Kubernetes.
4. Collect results - done using the Kubernetes' API.
5. Remove and clean up the created IaaS stack - done by Terraform with a single command.

All of the above is achieved using Python scripting as the "glue" for the system.

3.1.2 Abstraction

An abstraction layer (Docker containers on Kubernetes) is now provided, and it allows a highly heterogeneous set of tests and workloads to be deployed in a simple way. The tests are shipped in

Docker images which already contain all the dependencies, and as such they require very little configuration or preparation to run tests, provided the compute node is ready. Specifically considering some of the test cases previously deployed manually in HNSciCloud, the work done now in OCRE includes the containerisation of the test in full, together with associated scripts and dependencies. The approach uses Kubernetes to deploy these docker containers easily (and remotely).

3.1.3 Managed Deployment

The deployment can now be achieved in a fully managed way. The user is not required to have experience on the underlying technologies, as the test suite framework hides such complexity. All configuration is done by setting two simple YAML files:

- *configs.yaml* - collects details about the authentication to the provider and the infrastructure provisioning.
- *testsCatalog.yaml* - collects details about the tests to be deployed and run.

3.1.4 Heterogeneous Catalogue

The set of tests deployed in HNSciCloud was extensive, even if focussed on IaaS infrastructure. The key tests used in HNSciCloud were, therefore, added to the validation tool. The increasing popularity of other cloud services, such as MLaaS and HPCaaS, made it important to include benchmarks on these as well so they could be validated for research workloads. As a result, the test suite now includes two distinct advanced machine learning benchmarks, both single- and multi-node (distributed) training of neural networks.

3.1.5 Container Orchestration Engines

The test suite is hosted in a single repository. A Docker image is offered, which bundles all the tools that are required to run the suite.

3.1.6 Central Collection of Results

Test and validation results are now collected on a S3 bucket hosted on the CERN cloud, which makes it possible to compare them historically between cloud platforms, and also cloud services within a single platform. This feature is optional and needs access the S3 bucket, which is not public.

Figure 3.1: Test Suite Overview

Figure 3.1 provides an overview of the whole framework, its relevant components, and the relations between them. The final product is a combination of third-party tools and test cases provided by the scientific community or partially self-developed by the CERN teams. The usage of technologies that are open and widely adopted by cloud providers makes it possible to deploy the tool on most of the available cloud platforms. The simplified configuration allows any user with different levels of technical expertise to deploy, assess, and compare cloud services by themselves in order to select the most suitable services.

3.2 Features

This section details the current list of integrated tests that are available in the tool's catalogue.

3.2.1 Deep Learning using Graphical Processing Units (GPUs): 3DGAN

The 3DGAN application [32] is a prototype developed to investigate whether a Deep Learning approach can be used to speed up the simulation of particle physics detectors. The benchmark measures the total time needed to train a 3D convolutional Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) using a data-parallel approach on distributed systems. It is based on Message Passing Interface (MPI) for communication. As such, it tests the performance of single nodes (GPUs cards), but also latency and bandwidth of nodes interconnects and data access. The training uses a Kubernetes cluster (GPU flavoured) with Kubeflow [20] and the MPI standard.

3.2.2 Deep Learning using GPUs: ProGAN

A similar test to the previously described one, the Progressive Growth of GANs test trains a ProGAN network using a single node strategy [29]. It uses a small dataset based on celebrities' faces and, once the model is trained, it can complete a missing quarter of an image of a face.

3.2.3 S3 Endpoint Tests

A simple S3 test script to test functionality of S3-like endpoints, checking:

- S3 authentication (access key + secret key)
- PUT
- GET
- GET with prefix matching
- GET chunk
- GET multiple chunks (key for datasets with a considerable number of files of various sizes).

3.2.4 Data Export: From the Commercial Cloud Provider to a Public Repository (Zenodo service)

When using cloud credits and the credit is near exhaustion, data can be repatriated or moved to a long-term data storage service. The example used in this test uses the Zenodo service [30] maintained by CERN, verifying that the output data can be moved from the cloud provider to Zenodo.

3.2.5 CPU Benchmarking

Suite containing several CPU-based benchmarks used for workloads from the High Energy Physics (HEP) community [31].

3.2.6 Networking Performance Measurements

perfSONAR [21] is a network measurement toolkit designed to provide federated coverage of network paths, and help to establish end-to-end network usage expectations. In this test, a perfSONAR testpoint is created using a containerised approach on the cloud provider infrastructure. The following tests are launched end to end:

- throughput - A test to measure the observed speed of a data transfer and associated statistics between two endpoints.
- rtt - Measures the round-trip time and related statistics between hosts.
- trace - Traces the path between IP hosts.
- latency - Measures one-way latency and associated statistics between hosts.

3.2.7 DODAS: Dynamic On Demand Analysis Services test

DODAS is a system that is designed to provide a high level of automation in terms of provisioning, creating, managing, and accessing a pool of heterogeneous computing and storage resources by generating clusters on demand for the execution of the HTCondor workload management system[22]. DODAS allows to seamlessly join public cloud resources to the HTCondor Global Pools such as the one of the CMS experiment [23] to enable the dynamic extension of existing on-premise computing resources to the public cloud. A benefit of such an architecture is the provision of high scaling capabilities and self-healing support that results in a drastic reduction of time and cost, through setup and operational efficiency increases. This test essentially checks the possibility to use DODAS on the provider to create an HTCondor pool.

More details related to these test cases and how to use the tool can be found in the official documentation of the testing framework [24] [25].

In addition to the catalogue, it is worth noting that a Docker image was created to collect all the code and third-party tools that are required to use the test suite. This saves the user from having to clone the repository and install tools. Instead, the user simply runs a single Docker command:

```
docker run --net=host -it cernefp/tslauncher
```

4 Test Contribution Process

As previously stated, the suite's test catalogue comprises test cases provided by the research community. The test contribution process that CERN has developed requires the test owners to:

1. Engage in a discussion with the test suite development team to present the test case. The objective of this is to better understand their proposal.
2. Take part in an assessment of the work to be done and requirements setup, in order to include their test in the test suite.
3. Provide information about documentation and contact details, and details about the license governing it. These details will be posted on the tool's documentation page and repository, to credit the authors (see, for example, in [\[26\]](#)).

By default, a test is plugged into the testing framework by using the test's Docker image. A different workflow may apply in cases where this is not possible, or where the Docker image does not exist.

5 Communication and Outreach

The test suite has been presented on several occasions (poster sessions, presentations, and technical demonstrations):

- **EGI Conference 2020** - Amsterdam, Netherlands 2nd to 5th November 2020 (Digital Event)
 - “Cloud benchmarking and validation test suite” demonstrated an example run of the suite, deploying its CPU benchmarking and network tests.
 - More information: <https://indico.egi.eu/event/5000/contributions/14359/>
 - Video: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZznFp9IIGR0>
- **CERN'S IT Technical Forum** - Geneva, Switzerland 29th May 2020 (Digital Event)
 - In a talk named “Cloud Validation Test Suite”, the main developers presented the suite to the Information Technology department at CERN.
 - Video: <https://videos.cern.ch/record/2719336>
- **ISC 2019** - Frankfurt, Germany 18th & 19th June 2019
 - Presented a project poster under the title “OCRE Cloud Benchmarking Validation Test Suite”
 - More information: <https://2019.isc-program.com/presentation/?id=proj136&sess=sess208>
- **First European perfSONAR User Workshop** - London, UK 5th June 2019

In a talk with title “Test and validation suite for cloud services”, the main developers presented the suite with a strong focus on its network test as it relies on perfSONAR, an open source network performance measurement tool. More information: <https://wiki.geant.org/display/perfSONAR/1st+European+perfSONAR+User+Workshop>

6 Future Work

Going forward, to carry out validation of cloud services under the OCRE Framework, access to the 27 cloud platforms will be necessary. CERN has proposed to include the obligation to provide access to a billing account with a limited number of funds made available by the cloud vendors of the original 27 cloud platforms represented directly or via resellers with contracts adjudicated through the OCRE Framework.

In addition, an extensive set of improvements and features are on the roadmap. these include:

- Provision of a mechanism for sharing the results of the tests with suppliers and users.
- Provision a dashboard for results' visualisation.
- Use Kubernetes deployment and/or Job instead of standalone pods.
- Avoid requiring a bastion server (support NAT).
- SSH key creation and population on the fly.
- Increase the configuration possibilities: networking, operative systems, stack versioning, etc.
- Update current tests and include new ones such as FAIRness evaluator, AAI tests, Data ingests, Migration Plans Assessment.
- Add technical measures validation for data processing, governance, and compliance (data location, data access permissions levels, etc.).

7 Conclusions

The test validation suite was successfully used to run tests in the following cloud providers:

- AWS (represented via a GEANT IaaS Framework reseller)
- Google Cloud Platform
- T-Systems' Open Telekom Cloud
- Exoscale
- Oracle Cloud Infrastructure
- CloudFerro
- Microsoft Azure (represented via a GEANT IaaS Framework reseller)

The test suite was also tested on open and free open standard cloud computing platforms such as OpenStack and CloudStack.

The test and validation framework has been partially deployed on CloudSigma (GEANT IaaS Framework reseller). The test suite was not successfully deployed on CloudSigma due to CloudSigma's lack of support of Terraform at the time this document was first written. After providing this feedback, CloudSigma in June 2020 included Terraform support on their platform via a verified provider [\[27\]](#). Validation will be done as part of the OCRE Framework.

The test suite roadmap is managed in a project hosted on CERN's Jira service. The test code and validation framework has been published under an AGPL license in a public repository online [\[28\]](#).

It will be important to maintain and expand the test suite beyond the lifetime of the OCRE project. CERN has proposed to the OCRE consortium to produce a test-suite roadmap for the EOSC as an additional OCRE deliverable, in view of the activities foreseen with commercial providers in EOSC FUTURE covering aspects such as data processing, governance and compliance (i.e., data location, data access permissions levels, etc.) and execution of exit strategies from commercial providers to avoid vendor lock-ins. This proposal is also aligned with the feedback received in the EC review in what concerns the OCRE outputs hand-over after the end of the project.

As part of the collaboration agreement between OCRE and EOSC Future, responsibility for the continued support and development of the test suite can be handed over from OCRE to EOSC Future together with the roadmap for future exploitation.

References

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Glossary

API	Application Programming Interface
AWS	Amazon Web Services
CPU	Central Processing Unit
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GAN	Generative Adversarial Network
GCP	Google Cloud Platform
GPU	Graphical Processing Unit
HCL	HashiCorp Configuration Language
IaaS	Infrastructure as a Service
IP	Internet Protocol
MPI	Message Passing Interface
R&D	Research and Development
SaaS	Software as a Service